

Terpenoids and Related Compounds. Part VI'. Triterpenoids of *Euphorbia Royleana*

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Glut-5-en-3- β -ol (IV), a stabilised intermediate in the biogenetic path from the cation (I) to friedelin (II), has been isolated for the first time from a natural source. Besides this, the isolation of other triterpenoids from the stem of *Euphorbia royleana* is reported.

The stabilised intermediates in the biogenetic path from the cation (I)² to friedelin³ are germanicol⁴, olean-13(18)-en-3 β -ol⁵, β -amyrin⁶, taraxerol⁷, multiflorenol⁸, isomultiflorenol⁸, multiflor-9(11)-en-3 β -ol, glut-1(10)-en-3- β -ol, glut-5(10)-en-3 β -ol (IIIa), and glut-5-en-3 β -ol (IV). Of these, the first five members have already been isolated from nature. Multiflor-9.11-en-3 β -ol and glut-1(10)-en-3 β -ol are unknown, but arundoin, the methyl ether of the former, has recently been isolated from *Arundo conspicua* and its structure has been established⁹. The remaining three compounds, viz., isomultiflorenol, glut-5(10)-en-3 β -ol (IIIa), and glut-5-en-3 β -ol (IV), have so far not been encountered in nature, although isomultiflorenol has been prepared⁸ from multiflorenol and the glutenols (IIIa and IV) have been prepared from glutinone (VI)¹⁰.

The present communication describes the isolation of glut-5-en-3 β -ol (IV) for the first time from a natural source.

Euphorbia royleana is a thorny plant of the *Euphorbiaceae* family, used as a fish poison. The stems of the plant have been shown recently to contain taraxerol¹¹. An investigation of the stem by us has led to the isolation of three crystalline compounds in traces along with taraxerol, glut-5-en-3 β -ol (IV), and a triterpenoid, m.p. 260-61°. The neutral fraction of the benzene extract of the dried stem was separated into petroleum-soluble and -insoluble fractions. The latter fraction was mostly taraxerol, which was purified and characterised as its acetate, m.p. 298-302°. The former fraction on chromatography provided the fractions recorded in Table I:

1. Part V, this issue, p. 539.
2. Ruzicka, *Proc. Chem. Soc.*, 1959, 341.
3. De Mayo, "The Higher Terpenoids", Interscience Publishers Inc., New York, 1959, p. 202.
4. Simonsen and Ross, "The Terpenes", Vol. 1V, The University Press, Cambridge, 1957, p. 247.
5. Musgrave *et al.*, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1952, 4303.
6. Ref. 4, p. 170.
7. Ref. 4, p. 276.
8. Sengupta and Khastgir, *Tetrahedron*, 1963, 19, 123.
9. Eglinton *et al.*, *Tetrahedron Letters*, 1964, No. 34, 2323.
10. Paton *et al.*, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1958, 2640.
11. Sharma *et al.*, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1964, 2, 254.

TABLE I

Eluent.	
1.	Petroleum-benzene (4 : 1)
2.	Do (3 : 2)
3.	Do (2 : 3)
4.	Do (1 : 4)
5.	Benzene-ether (1 : 1)

Eluate.	
(a)	Solid A, m.p. 228-40°
(b)	Solid B, m. p. 210-12°
	Solid C, m.p. 244-51°
	Solid D, m.p. 260-61°
	Crude glut-5-en-3 β -ol.
	Crude taraxerol.

The above crude glut-5-en-3 β -ol was purified through its acetate (V), m.p. 188-92°, which on hydrolysis furnished pure glut-5-en-3 β -ol (IV), m.p. 206-208°. The acetate (V) smoothly underwent proton-catalysed isomerisation to glut-5(10)-en-3 β -yl acetate (IIIb). Further, glut-5-en-3 β -ol on oxidation with chromium trioxide-pyridine complex¹² furnished glut-5-en-3-one (VI), identical (IR) with an authentic specimen.* Further, the O. R. D. curve^{**} of our glut-5-en-3-one was superimposable to that of an authentic specimen. The

12. Poos *et al.*, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1955, **77**, 1026.

* The authors are highly indebted to Dr. J. Mclean of the University of Strathclyde, Glasgow, for comparing (IR) their glut-5-en-3-one with an authentic sample from Dr. Spring's collections.

** The authors are highly indebted to Prof. Carl Djerassi of Stanford University, U. S. A. for comparing the O. R. D. curve of their glut-5-en-3-one with an authentic specimen and for the I. R. spectra of the authors' compounds.

analysis of the solid (D), m.p. 260-261°, in the above chromatogram corresponded to $C_{30}H_{50}O$. It shows a positive tetranitromethane test and a peak at 3600 cm^{-1} in the IR spectra, indicating that it is a triterpene alcohol with unsaturated linkage present. Further work on this solid and on solids A, B, and C, obtained only in traces, is in progress.

*EXPERIMENTAL

Benzene Extract of the Stem of E. Royleana.—The dried and powdered stem of *E. royleana* (1kg.) was extracted in a Soxhlet with benzene for 8 hr. The resinous mass after removal of the benzene was taken up in ether and the ethereal solution was washed with a cold 5% KOH solution and then with water and dried (Na_2SO_4). The neutral material (50 g.), obtained after evaporation of the ether, was digested with light petroleum (500 ml), allowed to stand for 18 hr., and filtered to yield a crude crystalline residue (15 g.).

Taraxeryl Acetate.—The above crude crystalline residue (5 g.) was chromatographed over activated alumina (200 g.). Elution with benzene-ether (1:1) mixture afforded a crystalline solid (3.2 g.), m.p. 256-76°, which was converted to its acetate by treatment with acetic anhydride (32 ml) and pyridine (32 ml). After working up as usual, the acetate was crystallised from a mixture of chloroform and acetone to furnish taraxeryl acetate, m.p. 298-302°, $[\alpha]_D +10^\circ$, identical (mixed m.p. and IR) with an authentic sample. (Found: C, 81.97; H, 11.04. Calc. for $C_{32}H_{52}O_2$: C, 81.99; H, 11.18%.)

Petroleum-soluble Fraction.—The above original petroleum solution (500 ml) after separation of crude taraxerol was placed on a column of activated alumina (500 g.). Elution with a mixture of petroleum and benzene (4:1) provided the following crystalline fractions: (a) solid A (10 mg.), m.p. 228-40°; (b) solid B (15 mg.), m.p. 210-12°.

Elution with petroleum-benzene (3:2) furnished solid C (25 mg.) which on crystallisation from acetone had m.p. 244-51°.

Solid D.—Elution with a mixture of petroleum-benzene (2:3) in the above chromatogram afforded a solid (30 mg.), m.p. 255-58°, which on repeated crystallisations from acetone furnished solid D, m.p. 260-61°, $[\alpha]_D \pm 0^\circ$ ($CHCl_3$). (Found: C, 84.50; H, 11.74; M.W. (Rast), 442. $C_{30}H_{50}O$ requires C, 84.44; H, 11.81%; M.W., 426). It shows positive test with tetranitromethane and a peak at 3600 cm^{-1} (OH) in the IR spectra.

Glut-5-en-3 β -yl Acetate (V).—Elution with a mixture of petroleum-benzene (1:4) in the above chromatogram provided a solid (1 g.), m.p. 178-94°, which was acetylated with acetic anhydride (10 ml) and pyridine (10 ml). After working up as usual, the acetate was crystallised from acetone, when glut-5-en-3 β -yl acetate (V), m.p. 188-92°, $[\alpha]_D +76^\circ$ ($CHCl_3$), was obtained (lit.^o m.p. 192-94°, $[\alpha]_D +79^\circ$). (Found: C, 81.97; H, 11.06. Calc. for $C_{32}H_{52}O_2$: C, 81.99; H, 11.18%). IR (KBr) peaks at 1730 and 1240 cm^{-1} (acetate).

*The petroleum used throughout the investigation had b.p. 60-80°.

Glut-5-en-3 β -ol (IV).—The above acetate (0.5 g.), m.p. 188-92° in benzene (20 ml) was treated with 5% KOH solution in methanol (20 ml) and the mixture was refluxed for 5 hr. After working up as usual, the solid was chromatographed over a column of activated alumina (40 g.). Elution with a mixture of petroleum-benzene (1:4) provided a crystalline solid, m.p. 198-202°, which after crystallisation from methanol furnished glut-5-en-3 β -ol (IV), m.p. 206-208°, $[\alpha]_D^{25} + 62^\circ$ (CHCl₃) (lit.¹⁰ m.p. 210-11°, $[\alpha]_D^{25} + 64^\circ$). (Found: C, 84.02; H, 11.60. Calc. for C₃₀H₅₀O: C, 84.44; H, 11.81%).

Glut-5-en-3-one (VI).—A solution of glut-5-en-3 β -ol (0.24 g.) in pyridine (2.4 ml), cooled to 15°, was added to a cold complex, prepared¹² from chromium trioxide (0.24 g.) and pyridine (2.4 ml), and the mixture was allowed to stand at the room temperature for 24 hr. After working up as usual, the gummy residue (0.2 g.) was chromatographed over a column of activated alumina (20 g.). Elution with a mixture of petroleum-benzene (4:1) furnished a crystalline solid (0.15 g.), m.p. 225-46°, which after crystallisation from a mixture of chloroform and methanol yielded pure glut-5-en-3-one (VI), m.p. 238-40°, $[\alpha]_D^{25} + 39^\circ$ (CHCl₃), identical (IR and O. R. D.) with an authentic specimen. (Found: C, 84.74; H, 11.26. Calc. for C₃₀H₄₈O: C, 84.84; H, 11.32%).

Glut-5-(10)-en-3 β -yl Acetate (IIIb).—Glut-5-en-3 β -yl acetate (200 mg.), m.p. 188-90°, was refluxed for 2 hr. with glacial acetic acid (40 ml) and HCl (conc., 6 ml). The reaction mixture on cooling deposited crystals which were filtered and recrystallised from a mixture of chloroform and acetone to furnish glut-5 (10)-en-3 β -yl acetate (IIIb), m.p. 291-95°, $[\alpha]_D^{25} - 18^\circ$ (CHCl₃) (lit.¹⁰ m.p. 297-99°, $[\alpha]_D^{25} - 23^\circ$). (Found: C, 82.24; H, 11.21. Calc. for C₃₂H₅₂O₂: C, 81.99; H, 11.18%).

The authors are indebted to the Council of Scientific and Industrial Research, New Delhi, for the award of a junior research fellowship to one of them (S. G.).

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Received April 2, 1965.

Recently Natori *et al.* of Tokyo have demonstrated (personal communication) that arundoin⁹ does not belong to this group of triterpenoids (added on the proofs).